

D9.2 Building energy use optimisation services – Month 18

Date : 17.02.2026

Deliverable No : D9.2

Responsible Partner : CIRCE

Dissemination Level : PU

Short Description	
D9.2: Building energy use optimisation services. 1st version of a detailed description of the building management systems enhancements, including new assets at sensor level, and advanced solutions at management level.	

Project Information	
Project Acronym:	WILSON
Project Title:	Distributed data modelling and Federated Digital Twinning for lifecycle data-driven sustainable operation and management of buildings and districts
Project Coordinator:	CIRCE
Duration:	48 months

Document Information & Version Management			
Document Title:		D9.2 Building energy use optimisation service – Month 18	
Related WP/Task:		WP9/Task 9.2	
Document Type:		Report	
Main Author(s):		CIRCE	
Contributor(s):		Project Consortium	
Reviewed by:		TUE, RINA-C and HSLU	
Approved by:		CIRCE	
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
V0	15.10.2025	CIRCE	First version created and corrected by Circe
V0.1	24.10.2025	TUE, HSLU and RINA-C	Review and correction of TUE, RINA-C and HSLU
V1.0	28.10.2025	CIRCE	Version corrections
V1.1	03.11.2025	CIRCE	Final version
V2.0	17.02.2026	CIRCE	Updated according to PO's comments

Disclaimer	
Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2.	INTRODUCTION	8
2.1.	Scope of the deliverable	8
2.2.	Structure of the deliverable	8
2.3.	Relation with other tasks and deliverables.....	9
3.	SCOPE, METHODOLOGY AND DEPLOYMENT PLAN	11
4.	LIVING LAB AND METHODOLOGY	13
4.1.	Building description and monitored system.....	13
4.2.	Methodological approach.....	15
4.2.1.	Data acquisition and preprocessing.....	15
4.2.2.	Predictive modelling and simulation	16
4.2.3.	Energy optimisation.....	18
5.	SMART CONTROL BASED ON COMFORT AND USE	20
5.1.	Definition of comfort parameters	20
5.2.	Thermal profile modelling.....	21
5.3.	HVAC control.....	25
5.4.	Lighting control based on occupancy and motion	26
6.	DEMAND RESPONSE AND FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT.....	30
6.1.	PV generation forecasting and monitoring	30
6.2.	Demand-GEN strategy.....	32
6.3.	Flexibility detection and calculation.....	34
6.4.	Analysis BESS in flexibility optimisation.....	36
6.5.	Integration analysis with district energy coordinator	38
7.	RESULTS AND KPIS.....	40
8.	CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS	43
9.	REFERENCES.....	45

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Diagram of structure of deliverable	9
Figure 2. Relation of T9.2 with other tasks and WP	10
Figure 3. Diagram of the scope of Tasks 9.2 and 9.3.....	12
Figure 4. External view of CIRCE’s headquarters	14
Figure 5. Building plant of CIRCE's Living Lab	15
Figure 6. Temperature data during a day	21
Figure 7. Daily thermostat overlay (winter vs summer)	22
Figure 8. Zone 4: Consumption vs temperature (15/02/2024)	23
Figure 9. Zone 4: Consumption vs temperature (18/06/2024).....	23
Figure 10. Thermal model validation - zone 4	24
Figure 11. Results of HVAC control	26
Figure 12. Consumption vs luminaire use	27
Figure 13. Luminosity per each zone with aggregated devices.....	28
Figure 14. Prediction of usage percentage for different lux level along a year.....	28
Figure 15. Solar generation data from CIRCE’s living lab (2022–2025)	30
Figure 16. Energy solar generation: Real 2025 vs Predicted	32
Figure 17. Consumption data from CIRCE’s living lab (2024).....	33
Figure 18. The predicted consumption vs predicted solar generation for Living Lab (April 2025).....	34
Figure 19. Flexibility analysis diagram.....	36
Figure 20. Interaction diagram with the district coordinator	39
Figure 21. WILSON Living Lab – Area of interest	40

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. WILSON variables for Task 9.2	16
Table 2. Summary of the most important indicators of the optimization methodology.....	18
Table 3. Metrics results from predicted generation	31
Table 4. Metrics results from predicted consumption.....	33
Table 5. Results of asset power density	41
Table 6. Results of asset use intensity	41
Table 7. Results of HVAC use intensity in different seasons	41
Table 8. Results of HCI.....	42
Table 9. Results of CCI	42

LIST OF ACRONYMS

AHU	Air Handling Unit
ARIMA	Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
ARX-type	Straightforward Predictive Model
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BMS	Building Management System
CDI	Cooling Degree Index
CRI	Color Redering Index
DHI	Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance
DSS	Decision Support System
EV	Electric Vehicle
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiance
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Condition
INSST	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
PDH	Personalise Data Hubs
PV	Photovoltaic
QoS	Quality of Service
R ²	R-squared
RD	Royal Decree
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RITE	Regulations governing thermal installations in buildings
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
T	Task
UC	Use Case
UGR	Unified Glare Rating
UHA	Air Handing Unit

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The report describes the work carried out on smart sensor systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort, the main objective of which is to define, implement and validate intelligent control strategies based on occupant comfort and real space usage, as well as mechanisms for managing energy flexibility in the pilot buildings of the WILSON project.

The document provides an overview of the work completed and planned for building energy use optimisation services. At this stage, the models to be developed throughout the two tasks are analysed, and the first optimisation and demand response models for the CIRCE Living Lab demonstrator are developed. First, the methodological approach applied to the demosites serving as a frontrunner is described, with a specific focus on the CIRCE Living Lab, selected at this initial stage due to its greater data availability and accessibility.

The methodology is structured in several phases. First, the data collected and the current legislation relating to workplaces are presented, serving as a framework for the Living Lab analysis. Next, the central building systems, such as Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC), and lighting, are described and optimised to maximise the comfort of the occupants and identify the margins of flexibility that can be exploited for more efficient energy management.

Once these systems are optimised individually, the methodology for demand response management and the overall flexibility of the building is introduced. This analysis integrates renewable energy, energy consumption, and electricity market prices, enabling 24-hour simulations and forecasts to evaluate the shiftable energy in the event of price peaks or other grid events. Additionally, the potential role of an energy storage battery is analysed, assessing how its operation could enhance self-consumption and reduce demand peaks or periods of low generation.

The general objectives for digital twin-enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy applications, as outlined in this paper, relate to building management and flexibility. As demonstrated in the document, an initial approach was developed using predictive models and control strategies. A thermal model was developed to capture the inertia of the building and support predictive control, complemented by photovoltaic generation and demand forecasting models that allow demand and generation to be coupled. Flexibility margins for air conditioning and lighting were quantified, and the potential of battery storage for self-consumption and peak reduction was assessed. These results provide a data-driven basis for optimising comfort, energy efficiency and coordination with the district layer.

Finally, the document provides a comprehensive overview of the upcoming activities, which will build on the results obtained. This next phase will focus on integrating and communicating between building-level control systems and the district coordinator, enabling multi-level energy management and coordination in the frontrunners. The data exchange protocols, interfaces and semantic structures necessary to ensure interoperability and secure communication within the project architecture will be defined.

This will enable the analysis of how coordination with the district affects each of the systems that comprise the building, according to their respective priorities.

2. INTRODUCTION

WILSON aims to facilitate the efficient and sustainable use of data in the built environment by combining innovative data management and analytics-based control. Unlike traditional approaches, such as conventional BMS systems based solely on reactive control and fixed rules, WILSON relies on the availability and diversity of data as the foundation for interdisciplinary services at the building and district scale. In previous phases of the project, demonstrators were analysed and use cases were designed to ensure results, while simultaneously seeking robust data pathways to examine the systems to be optimised and carry out development.

In this context, the report about smart sensor systems and analytics for optimal building use and comfort focuses on building-level intelligence to convert heterogeneous data into control actions and decisions that enhance comfort and energy performance. Given the parallel deployment of Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs), which is being developed, work has begun at CIRCE's Living Lab to validate the process and methods with full access to data and assets, ensuring that the solutions are reproducible and adaptable to frontrunners and other pilot projects.

2.1. Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable outlines the work carried out in CIRCE's Living Lab, where the building-level demonstrator was characterised, including the monitored systems and measurement topology, and the necessary data path for analysis and control was established. The workflow for data acquisition and pre-processing from a local database is detailed, as is the harmonisation of heterogeneous data sets, the quality controls applied and the aggregation of signals by zone/quadrant. The predictive modelling approach used to obtain the thermal profile per quadrant is also explained, together with the estimation of key physical parameters such as gain and time constant. Furthermore, it also presents the building-level energy optimisation layer, in which comfort objectives govern air conditioning and lighting and consumption margins are calculated to obtain flexibility windows.

Finally, the document describes the integration links with demand response services and the district coordinator, enabling signal exchange and an hourly re-optimisation loop. The final on-site implementations in the pioneering pilot projects are beyond the scope of this document; they will be carried out in future developments, once the PDHs are operational and the specific adaptations have been completed.

2.2. Structure of the deliverable

This document is organised into three complementary sections. First, an overview contextualises the task, explaining what is being developed during this work and what will continue in the next months, to understand the scope, functions and pilots. The 'Technological developments' section (Section 4, 5 and 6) forms the core of the document and presents all the technical work, including the Living Lab baseline, smart climate control and lighting, and demand response with flexibility and district coordination. Finally, the 'Conclusions' section summarises the results and describes how the work will be transferred

during the next months for implementation in the demo sites (Section 7 and 8). Figure 1 shows the structure of the deliverable organised according to the following sections:

1. **Global review** (grey). High-level view of the task: definition of developments, current scope, and the organisation of responsibilities and timing or completed and future work carried out within the context of building energy use optimisation services. It sets the context and objectives that frame the technical work.
2. **Technological developments** (orange). This is the most important part, where the development occurs:
 - **Living Lab description.** A presentation of the CIRCE Living Lab, including the building and systems used to develop the first solution, as well as the available datasets, metering and network topology, and the data pipeline that ensures quality and traceability.
 - **Smart control based on comfort and use.** Optimisation of thermal systems, HVAC (Heating Ventilation and Air Condition), and lighting, integrating comfort targets and energy savings: thermal profile modelling by quadrant, setpoint strategies, and control logic to maximise efficiency while maintaining comfort.
 - **Demand response and flexibility.** Modelling of generation and consumption, detection and calculation of flexibility windows, and the coordination workflow with the district coordinator, including hourly signal exchange and the re-optimisation loop.
3. **Conclusions and next steps** (blue). Summary of current findings and lessons learned, as well as the plan for continuing in next months: porting the methodology to the frontrunners, adapting it to PDH endpoints and validating the solution on site. This will enable the project to progress from this initial implementation to full deployment.

Figure 1. Diagram of structure of deliverable

2.3. Relation with other tasks and deliverables

This report builds directly on baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios, which provided pilot information, Key Performance Indicator (KPIs), and Use Cases (UC). During development, this baseline is applied to CIRCE's Living Lab, and the same

approach will be replicated at the frontrunners during the next developments. In parallel, PDH provides the secure data layer; our ingestion/normalisation pipeline and APIs are designed to operate on PDH endpoints, and the Living Lab setup mirrors this stack locally. All of this is shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. Relation of T9.2 with other tasks and WP

3. SCOPE, METHODOLOGY AND DEPLOYMENT PLAN

This deliverable falls under Task 9.2, which is being carried out between March and October 2025 (M10-M18) in coordination with Task 7.1 (Personalised Data Hubs (PDH)). The aim is to improve the Building Management System (BMS) in terms of both the quantity and quality of data and system intelligence by developing advanced analytics to optimise consumption and thermal profiles, taking into account Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) and external factors, as well as demand and occupancy/Renewable Energy Sources (RES) forecasting and providing optimal setpoint recommendations for comfort and efficiency. As the project progresses, each demonstrator will securely expose its data via the PDH, enabling other microservices to use it in accordance with the consortium agreement.

The main implementation focuses on the pilots' frontrunners (Spanish and Swiss pilot) of Innovations INN3 (P2P data and services marketplace) and INN4 (Semantic-aware analytics energy management toolset). This implementation will begin when data can be securely obtained through the PDHs developed in work packages 7 and 8 (WP7-8). To accelerate the development and validate the end-to-end methodology, a solution is being developed in CIRCE's Living Lab using internal data (historical and near real-time) under local control. This solution is being designed to be replicable and adaptable to each demonstrator's systems; at each site, we will perform a capability assessment to verify whether, with existing systems and available data, the expected performance can be achieved—or whether additional equipment (e.g., sensors, gateways, actuators) should be installed for optimal results. Part of this information was collected in WP4 (Baseline assessment and performance indicators of buildings and portfolios) and will be reviewed and updated during the current development phase.

Methodological scope of the work:

- Demonstrator characterisation at building level (location, applicable regulations, available HVAC/lighting systems, presence of batteries and electrical vehicle chargers (EV chargers), metering topology/counters and field buses).
- Data ingestion, harmonisation, and quality control via the PDH (or local source at CIRCE).
- Thermal profile modelling by quadrant using setpoints, ventilation/valves, occupancy (CO₂), and outdoor temperature as inputs.
- Building-level optimisation of HVAC and lighting: per-system control and consumption margin calculation to derive flexibility windows.
- Day-ahead (hourly) planning considers generation, consumption, batteries (if present), and market prices; the plan identifies flexibility windows (e.g., preheating to reduce expensive peaks, deciding between self-consumption and reserve).
- Building-district orchestration: The building plan is sent hourly to the district coordinator, who may return a green light or provide constraints. The system re-optimises in the next iteration to respect limits and maintain comfort.

This methodology is shown in Figure 3, which presents a very simple diagram illustrating how they are related, and which developments depend on task 9.2 or 9.3 and their integration.

Figure 3. Diagram of the scope of Tasks 9.2 and 9.3

This deliverable documents the initial phase at CIRCE’s Living Lab, where we have integrated and aligned the data to compute consumption profiles and develop the optimisation of HVAC and lighting, alongside the demand response system and flexibility management for effective coordination with the district. In the next phase (Task 10.2), the methodology and toolset will be progressively deployed across the pilot demonstrators once their Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) are fully operational and secured. The forthcoming activities will include: adapting the predictive and optimisation models to the specific data and sensor configurations of each pilot; validating the control strategies in simulated and real operating conditions; and (assessing performance through predefined KPIs related to comfort, efficiency, and flexibility).

4. LIVING LAB AND METHODOLOGY

This section presents the CIRCE Living Lab pilot building, describing its physical characteristics, available systems (e.g., HVAC, thermostats, luminaires, motion and occupancy sensors), and the monitoring infrastructure that supports it.

It also outlines the methodological framework that will be applied for the analysis, modelling, and development of data-driven energy optimisation strategies based on thermal comfort and operational efficiency.

The Living Lab serves as a controlled yet realistic environment where hardware and software solutions can be deployed, tested, and fine-tuned before large-scale implementation in real demonstration sites.

4.1. Building description and monitored system

The Living Lab is located at CIRCE's headquarters in Zaragoza, Spain, and consists of several offices and technical facilities within the same business area. During recent renovations, various innovative solutions were implemented, all of which are managed entirely by CIRCE.

This autonomy guarantees a flexible environment managed by qualified personnel, allowing for the testing of various solutions in the context of sustainability and energy efficiency [1].

Thanks to its great flexibility and extensive network of monitoring sensors, the Living Lab is an ideal environment for developing new solutions and testing different models of automation and energy optimisation. The combination of real-time data, device control and integration of renewable energy sources makes it particularly suitable for designing, validating and adjusting advanced control strategies before implementing them in real demonstration sites.

In particular, the living lab provides access to:

- Completely automated offices, with access to electricity consumption, temperature, humidity and air quality.
- Several RES equipment: 14.8 kW of photovoltaic (PV) on the roof, three electric vehicle chargers and easy access to vehicles to test and energy storage through batteries (5kW/18kWh)
- A centralised microgrid control that connects and controls all the previously mentioned equipment.

This facility (Figure 4) serves as the entry point for the deployment of the WILSON project tools. It acts as a technical sandbox, enabling the testing of hardware and software in real conditions while preventing delays in real demo sites.

Figure 4. External view of CIRCE's headquarters

Since 2022, the Living Lab has maintained a continuous historical record of measurements from multiple monitored systems, all integrated into a centralised database. The main categories of devices include lighting systems, air handling units (AHU), contactors, environmental sensors, energy meters, thermostats, HVAC equipment, solar generation units, and the main building energy meter.

Each device type provides a wide range of high-resolution measurements. For example:

- Lighting systems record luminosity levels, detect occupancy (presence sensors), and register on/off states to analyse usage patterns and optimise operation.
- Environmental sensors monitor indoor temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ concentration to assess comfort and indoor air quality.

All these devices and sensors are mapped within the building's internal layout (Figure 5), which allows correlating the data with the specific zones where events occur. This spatial mapping enhances the capacity to test location-specific optimisations, such as zone-based lighting control, targeted HVAC operation, or adaptive ventilation rates.

Figure 5. Building plant of CIRCE's Living Lab

By combining these capabilities, the CIRCE Living Lab provides a comprehensive, data-rich, and controlled environment that enables the entire cycle of energy optimisation development: from initial data exploration, through predictive modelling, to real-time control testing.

4.2. Methodological approach

The methodological framework applied in the CIRCE Living Lab is structured into three main phases: data acquisition and preprocessing, predictive modelling and simulation, and energy optimisation. This workflow ensures a continuous improvement loop where real-time measurements, predictive analytics, and optimisation strategies are interconnected.

4.2.1. Data acquisition and preprocessing

Data is obtained from a centralised database connected to the building's Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system, which integrates measurements from lighting, HVAC, thermostats, environmental sensors, solar PV systems, energy meters, and EV chargers.

The SCADA interface provides both:

- Historical data (since 2022), enabling long-term trend analysis and training of machine learning models.

- Real-time data (updated every 5 minutes), supporting online monitoring and control actions.

Sensors are distributed across all working zones and technical areas, allowing zonal analysis and location-specific optimisation. The preprocessing pipeline includes:

- Timestamp homogenisation: Aligning data from different devices to a common temporal resolution, typically aggregating to 1-hour intervals for long-term trend analysis and keeping 5-minute resolution for short-term prediction tasks.
- Data cleaning and gap filling: Handling missing values, correcting outliers, and synchronising different data streams. For gap filling, statistical methods and interpolation are applied, and when needed, predictive imputation models are used.
- Feature engineering: Creation of derived variables such as cumulative daily irradiance, temperature-irradiance interaction terms, and lagged variables for capturing temporal dependencies.

4.2.2. Predictive modelling and simulation

The initial modelling stage focuses on predicting energy consumption, PV generation, and electricity market prices, as these three components directly influence flexibility strategies. Python libraries and functions are used to develop all models, with a view to facilitating future connection to the PDH and data space.

For PV generation prediction, two parallel approaches are considered:

- Physical simulation models based on irradiance and PV system parameters, producing a baseline estimation.
- Machine learning models trained on historical data. During the initial phase, different regression algorithms were tested, including Random Forest and Linear Regression, to compare their performance and robustness. The results of these comparisons can be found in Section 6.1. Ultimately, XGBoost was selected as the primary model due to its superior optimisation capabilities, resilience to overfitting, and strong performance when dealing with complex and highly variable datasets. The models obtained will be validated using error metrics (MAE, RMSE, R2...) in addition to other validation methods such as comfort rule checks and confidence bands. Further exploration of alternative models and hybrid approaches will continue in Task 10.2, building on the results obtained in this phase.

The following table (Table 1) presents the variables used in the predictive model and simulation, which include variables related to irradiance and outdoor weather conditions, as well as occupancy components and indoor environmental conditions.

Table 1. WILSON variables for Task 9.2

Variable	Description	Location	Units
Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI)	Total solar radiation received on a horizontal surface	Outdoor	W/m^2

Variable	Description	Location	Units
Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI)	Solar radiation received per unit area perpendicular to the sun's rays	Outdoor	W/m^2
Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI)	Diffuse solar radiation received on a horizontal surface (scattered light)	Outdoor	W/m^2
Ambient temperature	Outside air temperature measured near the building	Outdoor	$^{\circ}C$
Wind Speed	Air velocity affecting convective heat transfer	Outdoor	m/s
Irradiance ratios	Ratios such as DNI/GHI or DHI/GHI, used to characterize sky conditions	Outdoor	-
Cumulative daily energy	Total daily solar energy integrated from irradiance values	Outdoor	kWh/m^2
Temperature	Air temperature inside monitored zones	Indoor	$^{\circ}C$
Humidity (RH)	Relative humidity within indoor spaces	Indoor	%
CO₂ concentration	Carbon dioxide level, proxy for occupancy and air quality	Indoor	ppm
Occupancy	Binary or percentage indicator of space occupancy	Indoor	- or %
HVAC operational state	Status or power level of heating, ventilation and cooling systems	Indoor	On/Off or W
Lighting operational state	Status or power consumption of lighting systems	Indoor	On/Off or W
Other electrical loads	Status or consumption of plug loads, equipment, etc.	Indoor	kW
Day of week	Categorical variable indicating weekday/weekend patterns	Derived	-
Season indicator	Winter or summer for HVAC systems	Derived	-

Where applicable, time-series models such as ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) and LSTM neural networks (Long short-term memory neural network) are considered for short-term forecasts, especially for highly autocorrelated variables like load demand. For market price forecasting, external datasets from market operators are integrated, enabling the creation of price prediction models for flexibility assessment.

4.2.3. Energy optimisation

Once the prediction models are validated, the next step involves defining and evaluating optimisation strategies, aimed at:

- Reducing energy consumption without compromising occupant comfort.
- Increasing self-consumption of photovoltaic (PV) energy and reducing grid dependency.
- Maximising the economic benefit derived from flexibility participation or demand response mechanisms.

The optimisation methodologies under consideration include:

- Rule-based control strategies: these rely on predefined rules based on thresholds or specific conditions (e.g., switching off HVAC when spaces are unoccupied or when outdoor temperature is favourable). They serve as a baseline reference, since they do not require predictive models and their behaviour is easily interpretable.
- Model Predictive Control (MPC): this approach uses trained predictive models (e.g., XGBoost) to anticipate the evolution of demand and generation, adjusting HVAC or lighting setpoints optimally. Its goal is to maintain comfort within predefined limits while minimising energy consumption or cost over a given time horizon.
- Heuristic optimisation algorithms (e.g., Genetic Algorithms): these allow solving multi-objective problems, where trade-offs between cost, comfort, and flexibility must be balanced. They do not necessarily yield exact solutions but are highly effective when dealing with large or complex search spaces.

To complement this qualitative description, Table 2. summarises the main measurable indicators that differentiate the three optimisation methodologies considered in Task 9.2. The more specific aspects of the models used for each system are developed in Chapters 5 and 6.

Table 2. Summary of the most important indicators of the optimization methodology

Method	Model dependency	Optimisation horizon	Computational complexity	Interpretability	Expected energy savings	Flexibility potential
Rule-based control	None	Instantaneous/ reactive	Low	High	Low– moderate (5–10%)	Limited
MPC	Optional (can use models as evaluation functions)	Short–medium term (hours to days)	Moderate–high	Medium	High (10– 25%)	High
Heuristic algorithms	Optional (can use models as evaluation functions)	Medium–long term	High	Low–medium	High (up to 30%)	Very high

Comfort refers to maintaining environmental conditions, such as temperature, lighting and air quality, within the limits defined by standards and occupant preferences. It is essential to consider comfort, as many energy-saving strategies can compromise thermal or visual comfort if these limitations are not taken into account.

Regarding the compatibility of objectives, they are not entirely mutually exclusive, but rather interdependent, as maximising photovoltaic self-consumption is usually consistent with reducing grid use and energy costs, provided that solar energy is available when needed. However, maximising economic benefit (e.g. through market price signals or energy exports) can conflict with maintaining comfort or self-consumption if market incentives do not align with periods of occupancy or generation. Therefore, optimisation is formulated as a multi-objective problem, in which heuristic methods and MPC approaches help identify optimal trade-offs between comfort, savings, and profitability.

5. SMART CONTROL BASED ON COMFORT AND USE

This section explains how the energy control strategy will be designed according to the thermal comfort and the actual occupancy of the building. The models for estimating thermal profiles, comfort parameters, and control mechanisms for HVAC and lighting, integrating sensor data and energy efficiency, are presented.

5.1. Definition of comfort parameters

In Spain, indoor environmental conditions for workplaces are governed by the General Workplace Decree (royal decree (RD) – RD 486/1997)[2] and its technical guidance from National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (INSST) [3], as well as the building HVAC code (RITE – Regulations governing thermal installations in buildings)[4] and the lighting design standard UNE-EN 12464-1. Together, they define temperature/humidity ranges, indoor air quality targets, and lighting criteria typically applied to offices.

- **Thermal conditions.** For sedentary office work, the INSST guidance to RD 486/1997 recommends operative temperatures of approximately 17–27 °C (winter/summer envelopes) and relative humidity of 30–70%, with limits on air speed to prevent drafts. These values underpin the usual comfort bands used in offices, which can then be narrowed operationally for energy control (e.g., 23–26 °C in summer; 21–24 °C in winter).
- **Indoor air quality (CO₂).** The RITE adopts the European comfort framework of UNE-EN 16798-1, which classifies indoor air quality (I–III/IV) using the CO₂ increment over outdoor levels as an indicator. Typical thresholds are ~550 ppm (Cat I), 800 ppm (Cat II), and 1350 ppm (Cat III) above outdoor CO₂ levels; Cat II is commonly used for standard office design/operation. Setting soft alarms around 900–1000 ppm is consistent with Cat II for usual outdoor backgrounds (~400–450 ppm).
- **Office visual tasks.** UNE-EN 12464-1 recommends a maintained illuminance of 500 lux at workstations, a UGR of ≤ 19 (glare), and a CRI of ≥ 80; ancillary areas (such as circulation and archives) can have lower illuminance levels. If energy or daylight controls are applied, targets can float (e.g., 300–500 lux) provided task quality, uniformity and glare remain within standard limits.
- **Occupancy & use windows.** Control setpoints must respect the actual occupancy schedule (e.g., 08:00–20:00 weekdays) and identify pre-conditioning windows (typically 1–3 h before occupancy, depending on the envelope’s thermal inertia) to shift load without comfort violations. This operational approach is consistent with the adaptive setpoint strategies outlined in EN 16798-1 and with the requirement of RD 486/1997 to maintain adequate conditions throughout the working day.

From standards to operational targets (for the Decision Support System (DSS)):

- Operative temperature bands: Summer 23–26 °C (target 24–25 °C), Winter 21–24 °C (target 21.5–22.5 °C), with a dead-band ±0.5–1.0 °C and ramp ≤ 1 °C/h to avoid discomfort spikes.
- Humidity: 30–60 % (inside the permitted 30–70 %).
- CO₂: soft alarm ~900 ppm and hard alarm ~1200 ppm (~Cat II/III thresholds depending on outdoor levels).

- Illuminance: 400–500 lux at workstations (maintained), Unified Glare Rating (UGR) ≤ 19 , Color Rendering Index (CRI) ≥ 80 . These two indicators directly affect visual fatigue and long-term visual comfort.
- Outputs to the Decision Support System (DSS): daily table with T_{min}/T_{max} , $CO_{2,max}$, lux_{target} , occupied time window, max ramp, and pre-conditioning window. These limits will bound the flexibility actions (pre-cool/heat, airflow trimming, dimming, or shifting of deferrable loads) evaluated in Section 5.3.

5.2. Thermal profile modelling

In this section, we develop the building’s thermal profile model by quadrants or zones—identifiers aligned with the loads and HVAC actions in the Living Lab. We unify and align the available temperature sources (room sensors, thermostats, and HVAC/AHUs), build a representative signal (T_{sens} : median per quadrant), and model its evolution using explanatory inputs such as setpoints, ventilation/valves, occupancy (as a CO_2 proxy), and outdoor temperature. Our goal is to develop a robust yet straightforward predictive model (ARX-type) and to estimate key physical parameters—gain and time constant, that capture the thermal inertia of each quadrant. This profile will serve as the foundation for the HVAC planner in 6.3 (preheating, maintenance, and savings), allowing us to quantify the impacts and expected savings when setpoints and schedules change.

Figure 6. Temperature data during a day

First, we evaluate the quality of the temperature data, which comes from three different sources: room environmental sensors (T, humidity, CO_2), the temperature collected by the thermostat, and the ambient temperature of the AHUs. We must confirm that these sources describe the same thermal phenomenon. As illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** (temperatures for one day in quadrant 4), we align all series in time and with the exact resolution (1 h) with a unified time zone, remove outliers and physical peaks, perform cross-comparisons by quadrant (correlation, bias, RMSE and possible delays using cross-correlation) and apply acceptance criteria ($corr \geq 0.95$; $|bias| \leq 0.6$ °C; $RMSE \leq 0.8$ °C). When consistency is confirmed, we adopt T_{sens} (median per quadrant) as the representative signal

and maintain T_{rt} and T_{uta} as validation/redundant sources, ensuring that the thermal profile is based on a reliable foundation and minimising bias and measurement errors.

Figure 7 superimposes two 24-hour thermostat traces (T_{rt}) for a winter day and a summer day on the same quadrant. In both cases, the system shuts down at night (with no active air conditioning), which can be observed in the gradual drift towards the building's free temperature. At the start of occupancy, the winter curve shows a clear heating ramp, while the summer curve stabilises through active cooling. During office hours, both traces form a plateau within the comfort band, indicating that the setpoints remain in line with office comfort standards and the programmed setpoint. For the rest of the thermal profile analysis, thermostat data is used as a representative temperature signal, as thermostats are distributed throughout the office spaces (capturing the occupied microclimate) rather than being located in the air treatment path (e.g., Air Handling Unit (AHU) return) or at a single environmental sensor points.

Figure 7. Daily thermostat overlay (winter vs summer)

In the first instance of developing an optimisation model that considers the building's thermal inertia, it is crucial to analyse the relationship between temperature and energy consumption. In this case, HVAC system consumption is obtained from aggregated meter readings per quadrant, while the average of different zone thermostats represents temperature. Figure 8 shows the energy consumption and temperature on a winter day. When the HVAC systems are turned off outside office hours, the energy consumption drops sharply while the temperature decreases gradually due to the building's thermal inertia. During peak occupancy hours, the consumption increases to reach and maintain the setpoint temperature. Figure 9 depicts a summer day. Here, the outdoor temperature rises during the night and early morning, forcing the system to work harder to stabilise the indoor environment at the setpoint temperature of 26 °C. This results in higher energy consumption during the central hours of the day.

Figure 8. Zone 4: Consumption vs temperature (15/02/2024)

Figure 9. Zone 4: Consumption vs temperature (18/06/2024)

As energy consumption is clearly related to the temperature of the building, and to study how to optimise control in HVAC systems in the next section, we will now focus on the thermal dynamics of each quadrant, where we are analysing a first-order discrete model.

$$T_{k+1} = a \cdot T_k + b \cdot T_k^{out} + c \cdot u_k + d \cdot occ_k + e$$

where:

- T_k is the indoor temperature at step k .
- T_k^{out} is the outdoor temperature.
- u_k is the HVAC power input (kW).
- occ_k is an occupancy proxy estimated from CO₂ concentration.
- a, b, c, d, e are coefficients identified via linear regression on historical data of temperature, HVAC consumption and occupancy.

This autoregressive model with exogenous inputs (ARX) captures the thermal inertia of the building: the indoor temperature at time $k + 1$ explicitly depends on its previous value T_k , reflecting how the building envelope and internal mass store and release heat in a delayed manner. By calibrating parameters per quadrant, the model provides both predictive accuracy and interpretability, serving as the foundation for subsequent optimisation and flexibility studies.

Figure 10. Thermal model validation - zone 4

From these results (Figure 10), it can be said that the future indoor temperature depends on its previous value, the outdoor temperature, the HVAC power supplied, occupancy, and a bias term. The estimated coefficients show a strong thermal inertia effect ($a=0.93$, with an approximate time constant of 15 hours), moderate coupling with the outdoor temperature ($b=0.059$), and a virtually zero contribution from both occupancy and the HVAC consumption signal ($c \approx 0$ and $d \approx 0$). This indicates that, in practice, the dynamics of the quadrant are dominated by thermal mass and exchange with the outside, while the current power signal does not sufficiently capture the influence of air conditioning.

In terms of simulation, the one-step-ahead adjustment yields a low error (RMSE ≈ 0.49 °C, $R^2 = 0.97$), indicating that the model accurately predicts the immediate evolution of the temperature when actual observations are available at each step. However, when propagating the model forward without feedback, the error increases (RMSE ≈ 1.55 °C), reflecting that the multistep prediction accumulates deviations and that the HVAC input signal is not acting as a reliable predictor of regime changes. In addition, the combination of heating and cooling conditions, as well as the absence of an explicit set point, contributes to the linear model losing explanatory power over long horizons.

In conclusion, the model effectively captures the thermal inertia of the building and its response to outdoor temperatures but requires improvements to more accurately reflect the operation of the HVAC system and the impact of occupancy. As next steps, we propose refining the HVAC power signal and separating heating and cooling modes and segmenting the identification into seasonal regimes (winter/summer, working days/holidays). These improvements will result in a more robust predictive model, suitable for integration into predictive control strategies (MPC) and for exploiting the thermal flexibility of the building in advanced energy management scenarios.

5.3. HVAC control

The HVAC systems play a key role in the energy performance and comfort conditions of buildings. To achieve this, it is essential to integrate temperature setpoints, occupancy profiles, thermal inertia and external factors such as outdoor temperature and electricity prices. In this section, we present the framework for controlling HVAC systems within the building, describing how predictive models can be leveraged and energy efficiency increased.

The main objective of predictive HVAC control is to maintain comfortable thermal conditions in occupied areas of the building while minimising energy consumption and associated costs. To this end, a prediction model is developed that describes the evolution of the indoor temperature based on external conditions, occupancy and the power supplied by the air conditioning system. The thermal inertia model developed in the previous point is taken as the starting point.

A finite-horizon optimisation problem is formulated using Model Predictive Control (MPC), where the profiles of u_k (HVAC power) and s_k (temperature setpoint) are optimised to minimise the total cost [5]:

$$J = \sum_{k=1}^H [\lambda_p price_k \cdot u_k \Delta t + \lambda_p (T_k - s_k)^2 + \lambda_r |u_k - u_{k-1}| + \lambda_h \phi(RH_k)]$$

Where:

- $price_k$ is the electricity price at time step k .
- Δt is the control interval length.
- $(T_k - s_k)^2$ penalizes deviations from the setpoint.
- $|u_k - u_{k-1}|$ penalizes abrupt changes in HVAC power (smoothness).
- $\phi(RH_k)$ measures the deviation of relative humidity from the comfort range (40–60%).
- $\lambda_p, \lambda_c, \lambda_r, \lambda_h$ are weighting coefficients that balance energy cost, comfort, smoothness, and humidity.

As mentioned above, as it is a workplace, it must follow a series of regulations, which is why the following limitations are considered:

- Thermal dynamics (review 5.2)

$$T_{k+1} = a \cdot T_k + b \cdot T_k^{out} + c \cdot u_k + d \cdot occ_k + e$$

- HVAC power limits

$$0 \leq u_k \leq u_{max}$$

- Comfort bands depending on occupancy

$$T_{min}^{occ} \leq T_k \leq T_{max}^{occ} \quad \text{if } occ_k > 0$$

$$T_{min}^{unocc} \leq T_k \leq T_{max}^{unocc} \quad \text{if } occ_k = 0$$

- Minimum ventilation in presence of occupancy (the occupancy level is currently an approximate value based on data obtained from other sensors, so it may vary)

$$u_k \geq u_{min}^{vent} \cdot occ_k$$

The results (Figure 11) obtained during the night interval indicate that the predictive model is capable of reproducing the thermal evolution of the quadrant without significant HVAC activation. The simulated temperature remains close to the initial value and within the limits defined for the unoccupied mode, with minimal power consumption ($u_k \approx 0$ kW). The *slack* variables (*slack_low* and *slack_high*) represent small tolerances allowed in the optimisation to prevent infeasibilities when the temperature approaches the comfort bounds. The presence of these *variables* close to zero confirms that, under these conditions, no relevant comfort violations occur and that the building's thermal inertia is sufficient to sustain the temperature overnight without additional energy costs.

	u_kw	s_C	T_pred_C	price_eur_kwh	occ	slack_low	slack_high
2024-06-18 00:00:00+02:00	0.000000e+00	25.780477	25.780477	0.04989	0.0	7.426859e-09	0.0
2024-06-18 01:00:00+02:00	0.000000e+00	25.588631	25.588631	0.03700	0.0	1.077331e-08	0.0
2024-06-18 02:00:00+02:00	0.000000e+00	25.420974	25.420974	0.05101	0.0	1.375467e-08	0.0
2024-06-18 03:00:00+02:00	0.000000e+00	25.257366	25.257366	0.05259	0.0	1.636533e-08	0.0
2024-06-18 04:00:00+02:00	3.336247e-11	25.093025	25.093025	0.05399	0.0	1.861301e-08	0.0

Figure 11. Results of HVAC control

Based on these results, it is advisable to recalibrate the thermal gain parameters and the maximum available power (u_{max_kW}) to avoid unrealistic results of zero or extremely low consumption, and to incorporate relative humidity more actively and CO₂ signals into the control model, as these variables directly affect comfort and ventilation in real-world scenarios.

5.4. Lighting control based on occupancy and motion

CIRCE's Living Lab is equipped with dimmable luminaires and zone-based presence control, where motion sensors activate the set of luminaires near the detector. In addition, each luminaire integrates a light (brightness measured in lux) sensor that measures ambient illuminance, which results from both natural light and the light emitted by the luminaires themselves. Historical data revealed inconsistencies in presence/occupancy logging. To mitigate this, we relate the presence signal to the luminaires active at each moment, thereby improving data coherence.

In relation to consumption flexibility, which will be discussed in the following section, each luminaire (by its ID) has been linked to its quadrant. This assignment allows us to cross-reference lighting data with energy consumption data from the meters assigned to those quadrants, enabling us to evaluate the potential savings that optimising lighting levels can achieve. At this stage, we are operating with relatively high set points; however, if consumption needs to be reduced, these can be lowered without affecting the user experience, while still complying with office lighting regulations.

All Living Lab data are pre-processed to ensure comparability:

- **Temporal harmonisation:** normalisation of date formats, conversion to the local time zone, and hourly resampling.
- **Luminaire signals:** calculation of hourly aggregate indicators and on/off classification under objective conditions (e.g., dimming level, measured lux, or command).
- **Quadrant integration:** simplification and aggregation of the series to relate them to the accumulated energy recorded by the meters in each quadrant.

As a first step in visualising the data, Figure 12 shows how the average usage percentage of the luminaires in quadrant 3 (left axis) evolves against the aggregate electric consumption of that same quadrant (right axis). “Usage” is defined as the hourly average dimming level (%) of all luminaires in the quadrant, consistent with the consumption figure, which is also aggregated at the quadrant level. Figure 12 presents the data for quadrant 3, which is formed for 12 luminaires, and the comparison is shown at one-hour intervals.

Figure 12. Consumption vs luminaire use

This visualisation reveals a clear correlation between the two series. The advance and delay effects observed can be explained by the 15-minute margin that each group of lights has after detecting a presence; after this detection, the light will remain on for the next 15 minutes.

To provide context, it is essential to demonstrate that the illuminance recorded by each luminaire’s sensor varies depending on the zone in which it is located. As illustrated in Figure 13, these measurements are influenced by both ambient light—depending on the position within the office—and occupancy levels, as a higher presence of people activates more luminaires. The figure presents the average illuminance per luminaire in each of the quadrants that make up the Living Lab, enabling a direct comparison of the light contribution across zones.

Figure 13. Luminosity per each zone with aggregated devices

To predict the flexibility available in the daily plan, it is necessary to understand how a change in the illuminance setpoint affects consumption in each zone. For this reason, two models are proposed: the first relates the usage percentage to illuminance, while the second refers to the energy consumption of each quadrant. The output of the first model incorporates seasonality, enabling us to estimate the expected usage percentage (dimming) as a function of the target illuminance (lux), time of day, and time of year. Figure 14 presents a prediction table by season, together with two examples: one for a winter day at 10:00 a.m. and another for a summer day at the same time. The results show that, for lower illuminance targets, there is a slight reduction in usage, although the difference remains limited.

```

Luminaire: 135
2024-01-15 09:00:00 2024-01-15 12:00:00 2024-06-15 09:00:00 2024-06-15 12:00:00 2024-12-15 09:00:00 2024-12-15 12:00:00
lux=100 76.954825 60.496291 76.463273 60.004739 77.25316 60.794626
lux=300 100.000000 86.776374 100.000000 86.284822 100.000000 87.074709
lux=600 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000
lux=900 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000 100.000000
Prediction: 2024-01-15 10:00
UseV @ 300 lux: 96.46108545160925
UseV @ 500 lux: 100.0
UseV @ 800 lux: 100.0
Prediction: 2024-06-15 10:00
UseV @ 300 lux: 95.96953338348656
UseV @ 500 lux: 100.0
UseV @ 800 lux: 100.0
    
```

Figure 14. Prediction of usage percentage for different lux level along a year

The reduction in illuminance setpoints, when analysed in terms of luminaire usage percentage, and consequently energy consumption, does not appear to have a significant impact on overall savings. This conclusion is consistent with the predictions from the energy consumption models, which also show only marginal reductions when lowering illuminance targets. In practice, tests have revealed that the built-in light sensors of the luminaires are not entirely precise due to their positioning, resulting in discrepancies in capturing the contribution of natural light. To improve this aspect and obtain a more accurate predictive model, it would be necessary to assess the feasibility of operating with lower sensor-based illuminance targets that genuinely affect consumption. According to current standards, the lower regulatory limit is 400 lux, a level at which the system already operates at nearly 100%

usage, leaving little room for effective optimisation. These results have been tested for different areas and days of the year, so we will analyse the possibility of taking light measurements with external sensors to check whether these light results are correct, adjust the setpoint, and re-analyse the usage percentages.

6. DEMAND RESPONSE AND FLEXIBILITY MANAGEMENT

This section discusses how to adjust the building's energy demand to match the available photovoltaic generation and how to calculate energy flexibility in real-time. It includes an analysis of the potential integration of a battery energy storage system (BESS) to enhance the system's efficiency and stability, as well as an examination of its interaction with the district coordinator.

6.1. PV generation forecasting and monitoring

In this phase, the generation data from CIRCE's living lab was used with the objective of building a model capable of forecasting solar production, which will be integrated into a decision support system together with consumption and electricity market values throughout this section. Initially, the available data were analysed and applied directly, without applying correction processes. Preliminary results showed a reasonable performance, although with significant limitations due to the lack of complete historical records and the presence of gaps of several consecutive days without data, as shown in Figure 15. The reason for this problem and the aggregation of data continues to be analysed.

Figure 15. Solar generation data from CIRCE's living lab (2022–2025)

With this in mind, different data correction strategies were tested to improve the quality of the historical series used for training the model. These included interpolations, daily moving averages, and adjustments using trend lines or linear regressions. The combination of these approaches enabled the reconstruction of a more complete and continuous daily series, which was subsequently used for modelling. To verify that the data were correctly filled after post-processing, it was confirmed that no days were missing and that the annual energy increased by 4.7%, while the statistical distribution of daily values remained stable (mean +3.9%, standard deviation -0.4%). The autocorrelation between consecutive days also improved (from 0.08 to 0.13), confirming a smoother and more coherent temporal behaviour of the dataset.

For prediction development, an XGBoost regression model was applied due to its ability to model complex, non-linear interactions, incorporating regularisation and iterative optimisation mechanisms that reduce overfitting and enhance predictive performance compared to simpler models such as linear regression, which are less suited to high-variability data. The model was trained on historical data from 2 August 2022 to 31 December

2024 (883 daily samples, 76.4% of the dataset), while the subsequent period from 1 January to 30 September 2025 (273 samples, 23.6%) was reserved as an independent verification set, allowing the predictive capacity to be assessed in a realistic forecasting scenario. Additionally, the possibility of integrating daily meteorological variables (irradiance, temperature, wind speed) was considered, although in this first version, the adjustment was performed exclusively with the generation series.

To validate the approach, several standard regression algorithms were also tested, including Random Forest, Support Vector Regression (SVR), and linear models ($R^2 < -0.1$; $RMSE > 1.9 \times 10^4$ Wh), which showed inferior overall performance when compared with the selected method. Only more advanced boosting-based implementations, such as LightGBM ($RMSE = 1.69 \times 10^4$ Wh; $R^2 = 0.15$) and HistGradientBoosting ($RMSE = 1.67 \times 10^4$ Wh; $R^2 = 0.17$), slightly surpassed its accuracy. These results confirm that ensemble gradient boosting algorithms provide the most robust framework for non-linear PV generation prediction, while simpler regressors tend to underfit high-variability data. The potential of these more complex models will be further analysed during Task 10.2, although at this stage, XGBoost has been selected as the reference predictive model for subsequent developments.

Preliminary validation results showed a good fit on the training set, with low errors and a stable behaviour in the verification phase, although accuracy could be further improved as more historical real data becomes available. Performance metrics for the processed data are summarised in Table 3. The results show a heterogeneous behaviour depending on the month: for instance, March and May achieved the best performance, with Mean Absolute Error (MAE) values close to 1100–2100 Wh, RMSE below 4700 Wh, and R^2 above 0.92, indicating a very accurate fit. January and February presented higher errors (MAE around 2600–2900 Wh and RMSE above 6000 Wh) but still retained acceptable explanatory power (R^2 between 0.79 and 0.88). April, however, displayed the highest errors (MAE > 5400 Wh and $RMSE > 8200$ Wh), likely reflecting a combination of data anomalies and variable weather conditions not fully captured by the model. Overall, the results confirm that the applied data correction significantly improves the reliability of the historical series and enables the model to provide robust predictions, particularly during months of higher solar production.

Table 3. Metrics results from predicted generation

	MAE	RMSE	R^2
January	2662,8	6009,1	0,887
February	2873,2	6151,0	0,794
March	2124,4	4613,7	0,926
April	5411,5	8214,4	0,815
May	1112,3	2725,3	0,943

Finally, different graphical representations were generated, comparing the real values against the predictions for various months in 2025, which illustrate the model's ability to capture both the general trend and the daily variability of photovoltaic generation (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Energy solar generation: Real 2025 vs Predicted

After analysing the results, the model still has room for improvement. The main limitation continues to be the scarcity and heterogeneous quality of historical data, which restricts the model’s generalisation capacity in certain months. As lines of improvement, it is a priority to expand the database with more complete records or to enhance the post-processing to achieve greater data continuity. The integration of external meteorological variables (hourly irradiance, ambient temperature, cloud cover) is also being considered, as they would allow for a better capture of daily variability. Likewise, comparing the current approach with other forecasting algorithms—such as recurrent neural networks (LSTM) or hybrid physics–data approaches—could help refine the adjustment and increase the robustness of the system.

6.2. Demand-GEN strategy

In parallel with the analysis of photovoltaic generation, the electricity consumption data from CIRCE’s living laboratory was analysed, as shown in Figure 17, which represents consumption in 2024 by time of year and day as a percentage. The objective of this section is to develop a predictive demand model, for which a procedure analogous to that applied to generation was followed, using an XGBoost regression model.

Figure 17. Consumption data from CIRCE's living lab (2024)

The results obtained show a more heterogeneous behaviour than in the case of generation, with R^2 values ranging between 0.65 and 0.90 depending on the month, as summarised in Table 4. These metrics indicate that, although the model can capture part of the underlying trend, demand forecasting is inherently more complex due to the higher variability associated with human usage patterns in buildings and the absence, in this initial version, of exogenous variables (such as work calendars, occupancy, or indoor conditions). For this reason, these results should be considered as an initial approximation, on which the model will continue to be refined.

Table 4. Metrics results from predicted consumption

	MAE (MWh)	RMSE (MWh)	R^2
January	12,0	18,0	0,905
February	9,0	13,0	0,891
March	31,0	51,0	0,711
April	17,0	26,0	0,807
May	31,0	51,0	0,653

To configure a Demand–Generation strategy, the predicted consumption and generation curves were compared for several months in 2025. As shown in Figure 18, photovoltaic generation is much lower than the total building consumption, representing only a residual fraction of the demand.

Figure 18. The predicted consumption vs predicted solar generation for Living Lab (April 2025)

For example, in April 2025, the calculated basic KPIs are as follows:

- **Total generation:** ~0.33 MWh
- **Total consumption:** ~679 MWh
- **Self-consumption:** 100% (all PV production is consumed locally in the building)
- **Excess generation:** 0 MWh
- **Deficit:** ~678.6 MWh
- **PV coverage of demand:** ~0.05 %

These results highlight that, under the current scenario, the PV contribution is practically symbolic compared to the overall demand. However, a 100% self-consumption rate is achieved, meaning that all renewable energy production is utilised locally without being exported to the grid.

Looking ahead, it is essential to move towards an hourly model of both generation and demand. This finer resolution will allow not only the evaluation of overall coverage but also the temporal synchronisation between production and consumption, which is critical for flexibility analysis and for the integration of electricity market signals, to be developed in section 5.3. It should also be noted that the current demand prediction does not yet account for the optimisation of equipment usage within the Living Lab, which will be integrated in future iterations.

In conclusion, this section establishes the initial diagnostic basis for the Demand-GEN strategy, in which current photovoltaic generation represents only a minimal part of demand, although it is completely self-consumed. In the following steps, the model will be further improved by including new explanatory variables (weather data, occupancy, working hours, additional sensors), as well as by optimising demand patterns. This will contribute to continuously improving the accuracy of predictions and enable a more detailed analysis of flexibility and optimisation, which is addressed in section 5.3.

6.3. Flexibility detection and calculation

In this section, we quantify the extent to which demand in the building can be modulated or shifted, complying with applicable regulations and maintaining the comfort conditions of the CIRCE Living Lab (tertiary use/offices). As a regulatory framework of reference, we

consider the RITE (Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings, RD 1027/2007 and amendments), the UNE-EN 16798-1 standard (indoor environmental parameters) and RD 486/1997 on occupational health and safety. Based on these restrictions, together with the actual operating programme, the expected photovoltaic generation and hourly energy prices, we constructed a reference curve without control actions. In addition to this reference, we define flexibility maps at the equipment level (e.g., air conditioning, dimmable lighting, deferrable loads) and identify useful windows for strategies such as preconditioning, setpoint/airflow adjustments, lighting regulation, or load shifting to times with lower costs or higher photovoltaic production. For this, we use the predictive models from section 5, in which the deferrable energy for HVAC and lighting systems has been calculated.

When drawing up a daily plan to organise flexibility windows, generation models, consumption forecasts and HVAC and lighting control models are used to forecast minimum and maximum consumption for the next 24 hours in one-hour intervals. To implement this plan, as mentioned above, historical data from the Living Lab are utilised. Occupancy is modelled with a bell-shaped profile that peaks between 10:00 and 15:00, accompanied by an out-of-office mode (the systems are mostly turned off), with a minimum safety temperature of 14 °C.

The flexibility margins of the systems are converted to kWh using an equivalent thermal capacity, which is limited by the ramp and the available net load. At the same time, we detect windows based on price (high/low) and proximity to occupancy periods (a 3-hour preconditioning horizon).

In practice, and as we have explained in the previous section, thermal flexibility is distributed between the UTAS/AHUs (ventilation/air treatment) and the fan coils/thermostats (terminal units), which are coordinated so as not to compromise comfort:

- **Fan coils/thermostats** (room temperature control). In addition to the hourly base setpoint, we apply reduction during high-price hours by raising the setpoint (max. 1 °C/h, within $[T_{min}, T_{max}]$); and preconditioning during low-price hours or before occupancy (respecting the ramp and comfort). Outside the office, they remain off and only operate for safety reasons if $T_{room} < 14$ °C.
- **UTASs** (air flow and supply temperature). During high occupancy hours, we propose a moderate reduction in ventilation (approximately 80% of the nominal value) and a slight increase in the setpoint within the established margins. During low occupancy hours and within the preconditioning horizon, we maintain nominal ventilation and adjust the setpoint accordingly. The supply air temperature is derived with a seasonal shift (summer: $T_{supply} \approx T_{sp} - 4$ °C; winter: $T_{supply} \approx T_{sp} + 4$ °C). Outside working hours, the AHU does not issue any commands, except in cases of safety necessity.

Flexibility in dimmable lighting is based on an hourly illuminance target and a dimming range that does not compromise visual comfort (section 5.4). Using the standardised history, we estimate the minimum level and expected dimming during peak hours (e.g. ~80% or the minimum that complies with lux) and maintain a nominal level during off-

peak/regular hours or when presence requires it. Outside the office, the set point is disabled (0%); however, as there are zone-level motion sensors, lights are turned on with priority when motion is detected to ensure safety and occasional use.

All of the above results in a daily plan that proposes the following actions, hour by hour: preconditioning during low-price or concern hours (controlled decrease in setpoint), reduction during high-price hours (increase in setpoint within the comfort range), AHU ventilation/supply adjustments (moderate reduction during high prices; nominal during low prices) and lighting dimming respecting minimums and switching off outside operating hours. In this way, although no adjustment of the lighting system has been achieved in the current Living Lab case, it is implemented in the daily plan in view of the possibility of future improvements. Finally, once the priority criteria have been established, the actions are ordered according to the possible responses of the district coordinator, which will be discussed in section 6.5. These actions will also be sent to the SCADA system, which coordinates the building's assets and executes the actions. Both the plan and the proposed commands are stored in JSON format for traceability and review. This database quantifies the available flexibility and implements it in a schedule plan, which serves as a starting point for future improvements. To illustrate this at a glance, the diagram in Figure 19 has been designed, showing the data needed to develop the daily plan and building flexibility calculations, as well as comments from the district coordinator.

Figure 19. Flexibility analysis diagram

6.4. Analysis BESS in flexibility optimisation

This section presents a case study for using a building-owned battery energy storage system (BESS), acknowledging that in some scenarios, storage may be managed at the building level—although it is more common to operate it at the district level. The aim is to demonstrate how it would provide flexibility and cost reduction without compromising comfort, safety, or regulatory compliance, and how it would integrate into the existing decision-making flow already defined for the CIRCE Living Lab.

The architecture always relies on the building's DSS, which issues charge and discharge commands for the BESS through this system, either following the hourly limits/acceptances from the district coordinator or operating autonomously with local data. This design facilitates replicability, as the same control module operates by changing only the source of constraints (coordinator or internal policies), while maintaining the integration point and telemetry unchanged.

Operationally, once the day-ahead plan is generated (Section 5.3) (24 h, 1-hour resolution) with forecasts of price, PV generation, and demand, the DSS decides each hour how to use the BESS based on three simple criteria:

- **Auto-consumption surplus and available capacity.** Charging the battery is prioritised to increase self-consumption and avoid curtailment.
- **Low prices, high generation and high demand.** It may be advantageous to buy electricity from the grid at a low price and store the building's own PV energy in the BESS for less favourable hours.
- **High prices.** Discharge within limits to minimise grid purchases. In this way, the BESS broadens the flexibility band by reducing grid consumption when the price is high and increasing it when the price is low, without altering thermal or lighting setpoints.

To ensure safe and traceable control, the DSS accounts for the BESS technical constraints (energy capacity, maximum charge/discharge power, round-trip efficiency, state-of-charge limits, no simultaneous charge/discharge, and ramps), an operational SoC reserve for contingencies, and—if applicable—the degradation cost per cycle. Anti-export policies are respected where they exist, and coherence with the thermal and lighting plan is maintained.

In building district coordination, the building's hourly message will include its expected baseline consumption and flexibility band, already incorporating the BESS contribution, along with HVAC and lighting. The coordinator may accept, limit, or reject the proposal based on network needs; the DSS then re-optimises and issues the next-hour dispatch, keeping the commitment within the agreed limits.

As an initial strategy, a transparent and fast heuristic is proposed: sort hours by price; schedule charging in cheap hours up to a target State of Charge (SoC) ahead of expensive hours; schedule discharging in expensive hours down to a minimum target SoC; override to absorb PV surplus even if it is not the cheapest hour when doing so avoids curtailment; always respect power limits and the constraints imposed by the coordinator or internal policies; and preserve a minimum SoC reserve for contingencies. Later, this logic can evolve into a formal optimisation that minimises cost plus degradation under PV and demand uncertainty.

Expected benefits include energy arbitrage (savings achieved by shifting kWh from expensive to cheaper hours), increased PV self-consumption, reduced curtailment, peak shaving (lower peak power), an expanded net flexibility band reportable to the district, and potential CO₂ reduction, if weighted by hourly intensity. The indicators to monitor include daily savings (€/day), self-consumption rate, reduced peak demand (kW), functional net flexibility, equivalent cycles/day, and degradation cost.

The incorporation of a building-owned BESS into the decision-making process increases available flexibility and reduces costs without compromising comfort. Channelling all decisions through the DSS makes the solution naturally replicable, whether a district coordinator is involved. It paves the way for more advanced optimisation as more data and requirements become available.

6.5. Integration analysis with district energy coordinator

Throughout the task, work has been carried out at the building level so far, but each building in the demonstrators is coordinated at the district level. Therefore, throughout this analysis, we defined a coordination channel between the building (CIRCE Living Lab) and the district coordinator. Every hour, the building shares its consumption commitment and flexibility window for the next 24 hours and receives an instruction indicating whether it can operate at minimum, maximum, or only part of its flexibility band. In this way, the local DSS replans in real time without compromising comfort or safety.

To ease future coordination, we set an operational resolution of 1 hour and a 24-hour rolling horizon, continually re-optimised to incorporate new information (prices, PV generation, occupancy). All coordination is anchored to Europe/Madrid, using ISO 8601 timestamps with time zones to avoid ambiguities (DST changes) and ensure traceability. For the information exchange, each building sends hourly a JSON with 24 entries, one per future hourly interval, including:

- **datetime:** interval start in ISO-8601 with time zone (e.g., 2025-01-15T13:00:00+01:00),
- **min-demand:** minimum feasible energy for that interval (kWh),
- **max-demand:** maximum allowed energy under comfort/safety (kWh).

For each interval, the coordinator returns the authorised building consumption, which can be:

- **MINIMUM:** operate at min-demand; the daily plan is regenerated to shift the operating window if needed.
- **MAXIMUM:** Operate at maximum demand; the daily plan remains unchanged.
- **PARTIAL:** operate within the band but with an intermediate cap due to district needs (peaks, congestion, price signals, etc.). In this case, actions follow the stated priorities, and the daily plan is regenerated to compensate.

This defines the operational and coordination plan with the following phases (Figure 20.):

- **Local plan (t).** The DSS computes/updates a 24-hour plan, deriving min_demand and max_demand for the next hour (after considering prices, PV, and occupancy).
- **Hourly offer.** The JSON above is sent for the next 24 h.
- **Coordinator instruction.** Reply per interval: MINIMUM / MAXIMUM / PARTIAL (with cap).
- **Local adjustment.** The DSS selects the action that maximizes value while respecting the priority order: (1) safety, (2) comfort, (3) cost, (4) wear; and ensures the next-hour commitment stays within the accepted band.
- **Execution & telemetry.** The dispatch is executed; consumptions, setpoints and states are logged; the next re-optimisation uses this telemetry. If the channel fails, contingency rules apply (e.g., safe baseline) and the event is recorded.

Figure 20. Interaction diagram with the district coordinator

This approach lays the groundwork for building district coordination: a continuous 24-hour cycle, a shared metric vocabulary, and a defined messaging & security scheme. It enables algorithm development and validation with real data and, once communication is active, an agile, low-friction deployment with clear traceability and contingencies—scalable to finer resolutions and to coordinator-driven signals/events. Furthermore, Figure 20 shows, in a simple way, the integration with the data space and the PDH, from which the data will be obtained securely from the pilots in the implementation of Task 10.2.

7. RESULTS AND KPIS

The activities carried out throughout Task 9.2 led to characterise the thermal profile by quadrants and develop an ARX model that captures the thermal inertia of the building and its relationship with the outside temperature and HVAC consumption for the CIRCE Living Lab. The results show a good one-step-ahead fit (RMSE < 0.5 °C; $R^2 \approx 0.97$), making the approach suitable as a basis for predictive control and for quantifying flexibility. Limitations have been identified related to the HVAC power signal (underrepresented or mixing modes) and the coexistence of heating and cooling regimes in the same model, reinforcing the need to enrich data and segment identification.

Progress has been made in two areas: predicting and refining PV generation (section 6.1), using an XGBoost model trained on corrected series; and demand prediction (section 6.2), which is more heterogeneous due to its dependence on human usage. These two areas have enabled us to evaluate a Demand-GEN strategy in which PV covers only a very small fraction of demand. This validates the focus on time optimisation and flexibility to improve production-demand coupling. The thermal and lighting flexibility margins (section 6.3) have been defined and quantified in terms of regulations and comfort. The integration of a BESS (section 6.4) has also been outlined to increase self-consumption, arbitrage, and peak shaving. Finally, the operational coordination scheme with the district (section 6.5)—hourly messages with a min-max band and immediate local replanning—has been described, laying the foundation for exchange via MQTT.

Based on the tests and analyses carried out, some of the KPIs identified for the innovations involved in this task [8] have been calculated. It is important to note that, although we worked with real data and predictions during Task 9.2, these have not been implemented in the actual operation of the CIRCE Living Lab. These KPIs will help evaluate the results subsequently achieved. It is essential to emphasise that, as this is a highly automated building, the most significant results will be completed by the frontrunners in Task 10.2. Figure 21 shows a diagram of the Living Lab and the distribution of areas representing the ‘area of interest’ used as variables in the energy management KPIs.

Figure 21. WILSON Living Lab – Area of interest

- **Energy management:**

- Asset power density.

$$\text{Asset power density} = \frac{\text{Total asset power for AoI (W)}}{\text{AoI – Area of interest (m}^2\text{)}}$$

Table 5. Results of asset power density

Asset power density	(W/m ²)
Zone 1	12,05
Zone 2	17,42
Zone 3	22,54
Zone 4	6,33

- Asset use intensity.

$$\text{Asset use intensity} = \frac{\text{Asset energy consumption (kWh)}}{\text{reference unit}}$$

Table 6. Results of asset use intensity

Asset use intensity	(W/m ²)
Zone 1	1.556,22
Zone 2	2.209,57
Zone 3	3.072,08
Zone 4	654,00

- HVAC use intensity
 - Winter season

$$\text{HVAC use intensity} = \frac{\text{Consumption (kWh)}}{\text{heating area(m}^2\text{)} / \text{Heating degree days (HSS)}}$$

- Cooling season

$$\text{HVAC use intensity} = \frac{\text{Consumption (kWh)}}{\text{cooling area(m}^2\text{)} / \text{Cooling degree days (HSS)}}$$

Table 7. Results of HVAC use intensity in different seasons

Area	Heating season	Cooling season
Zone 1	0,0058	0,0136
Zone 2	0,0084	0,0206
Zone 3	0,0111	0,0257
Zone 4	0,0028	0,0071

- **Comfort**

- Heating comfort index (HCI) (sample 24h)

Table 8. Results of HCI

$$HCI = \sum (T_{comfort} - T_{actual}) * \Delta t$$

Heating comfort index	HCI
2024-02-01	4,12
2024-02-05	2,98
2024-02-09	2,96
2024-02-16	10,85

- Cooling comfort index (CCI) (sample 24h)

Table 9. Results of CCI

$$CCI = \sum (T_{actual} - T_{comfort}) * \Delta t$$

Heating comfort index	CCI
2024-02-01	88,63
2024-02-05	84,13
2024-02-09	88,27
2024-02-16	5,06

- Renewable energy (Generation point – 100% auto consumption)

8. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The results achieved demonstrate significant progress towards the objectives of WP9, particularly in enhancing the intelligence of Building Management Systems through data-driven optimisation, predictive control, and flexibility assessment. The combination of the thermal profile, demand and photovoltaic energy forecasting, and flexibility quantification provides a comprehensive framework for improving energy efficiency and occupant comfort, while enabling interaction with the district at the district level through secure communication protocols. These outcomes establish a robust foundation for the subsequent developments during next months, where the methodologies and control strategies defined here will be validated and deployed in real operating conditions across the pilot sites.

The next development phase focuses on improving the accuracy and robustness of the predictive models. This involves applying ARX/MPC approaches by regime, distinguishing between winter and summer conditions as well as working days and holidays, and differentiating heating and cooling operations in the HVAC signal. The treatment of delays and setpoints will be enhanced by adding explicit lag variables and setpoint errors, while exploring the use of observers or Kalman filters to ensure multi-step stability. Furthermore, additional exogenous variables such as relative humidity, occupancy schedules, ventilation rates, and weather parameters (irradiance, outdoor temperature, and cloud cover) will be incorporated into both demand and generation models. Continuous validation will be performed through rolling train/test cycles by month and seasonal model re-identification to maintain performance over time.

Future work will also focus on demand-generation coupling and real-time flexibility scheduling. Synchronisation of measurements and execution times will be addressed to ensure reliable communication between systems. The demand model will be expanded by integrating exogenous variables such as calendar events, occupancy levels, and indoor environmental parameters. The flexibility engine will be improved so that actions are executed dynamically based on the responses received from the district coordinator. In addition, coordinated control rules will be implemented for AHUs (UTAs) and terminal units, optimising setpoints and airflow rates, and integrating lighting dimming control based on both lux levels and occupancy detection.

Another key area will be coordination with the district and MQTT-based communication. Coordination with the district layer will rely on the exchange of JSON hourly messages (24 intervals) containing key parameters such as datetime, minimum and maximum demand, and—when applicable—the state of charge of the battery energy storage system (SoC/BESS). Communication will be established through a secure Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol with agreed topics, defined Quality of Service (QoS) levels, and contingency management procedures. A 24-hour/1-hour rolling operational loop will ensure continuous interaction between the building and the district coordinator.

Finally, deployment in demonstrators and adaptation to local data will follow a progressive approach across the pilot sites, with parameters adapted to each building's climate, schedules, capacities, operational limits, and site-specific policies (e.g., anti-export

constraints). The deployment process will advance through sequential phases of simulation, controlled field testing, and assisted operation, with quarterly review cycles to monitor progress. The impact of the implemented strategies will be evaluated through key performance indicators, including energy and economic savings (€/kWh), comfort level compliance, net flexibility, PV self-consumption, and avoided CO₂ emissions.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission, WILSON Partners *D4.1 – Detailed models of buildings at demonstration pilots*. WILSON. Bruxelles: European Commission, 2024. HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-02 – Project 101147267.
- [2] AGENCIA ESTATAL BOLETÍN OFICIAL DEL ESTADO. Real Decreto 486/1997, de 14 de Abril, Por el Que se Establecen Las Disposiciones Mínimas de Seguridad y Salud en Los Lugares de Trabajo. 1997.
- [3] INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE SEGURIDAD E HIGIENE EN EL TRABAJO (INSHT). Guía técnica para la evaluación y prevención de los riesgos relativos a la utilización de los lugares de trabajo. 2015.
- [4] España. *Real Decreto 178/2021, de 23 de marzo, por el que se modifica el Reglamento de Instalaciones Térmicas en los Edificios, aprobado por Real Decreto 1027/2007, de 20 de julio*. Boletín Oficial del Estado, nº 71, 24 de marzo de 2021, pp. 36669–36760. Disponible en: <https://www.boe.es/eli/es/rd/2021/03/23/178> [Accessed: Oct. 2025]
- [5] SERALE, Gianluca, et al. Model predictive control (MPC) for enhancing building and HVAC system energy efficiency: Problem formulation, applications and opportunities. *Energies*, 2018, vol. 11, no 3, p. 631.
- [6] TAHERI, Saman. *Energy Optimization of Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning Systems*. Purdue University, 2024.
- [7] European Commission, WILSON Partners *D9.3 District-level and grid optimisation services*. WILSON. Bruxelles: European Commission, 2024. HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-02 – Project 101147267.
- [8] European Commission, WILSON Partners *D4.5 – WILSON KPIs life-cycle oriented indicators panel*. WILSON. Bruxelles: European Commission, 2024. HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-02 – Project 101147267.

wilson-project.eu

wilson-project

wilson-project

wilson_project_

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101147267